

DELIVERABLE

Project Acronym: Q-SORT
Grant Agreement number: 766970
Project Title: Q-SORT. The Quantum Sorter: A New Measurement Paradigm in Electron Microscopy

Manuscript for paper or report on theory advances/test on diagonalization of operator through coordinate transformation (release 2)

D3.2

Version: Final

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Project funded by the European Commission within the FET OPEN Programme		
Dissemination Level		
P	Public	x
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Revision History

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	29 May 2019	Vincenzo Grillo	CNR	Structure of the document
0.2	11 June 2019	Vincenzo Grillo	CNR	Initial draft – Chapter 1
0.3	21 June 2019	Miles Padgett & Daan Stellinga	UG	Draft - Chapters 2,3,4
0.4	10 July 2019	Enzo Rotunno Vincenzo Grillo Stefano Frabboni	CNR UMR	Comments on draft of chapters 2, 3,4
0.5	25 July 2019	Miles Padgett & Daan Stellinga	UG	Revision of draft chapters 3,4,5
0.6	06 August 2019	Enzo Rotunno & Vincenzo Grillo Stefano Frabboni	CNR UMR	Revision draft chapter 1
0.7	10 September 2019	Enzo Rotunno & Vincenzo Grillo Miles Padgett & Daan Stellinga	CNR UG	Consolidated version Chapters 1,2,3,4
0.8	18 September 2019	Vincenzo Grillo	CNR	Integration of all contributions and conclusions
0.9	26 September 2019	Roberto Balboni Amir Tavabi	CNR FZJ	Review
1	29 September 2019	V. Grillo	CNR	Final version integrating feedback from the reviewers

Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable D3.2, “Manuscript for Paper or Report on Theory Advances/Test on Diagonalization of Operator through Coordinate Transformation (release 2)” is used to conclude and refine the topics identified in the previous release of the same deliverable.

It lays the appropriate theoretical basis for the definition of a generalized sorter that would allow for the recognition of the protein without making a full image it.

We called this process *diagonalization*, since the image of the protein should result in an abstract set of pixels, like a diagonal matrix.

The results described in this deliverable are of the utmost importance in view of the final experiments of reconstruction of the proteins as foreseen in WP5. This problem is very difficult to tackle for proteins that typically produce a small phase change.

In order to improve its readability, the current document is structured as a series of papers .,

It must be pointed out that most of the approaches hereby presented are mature enough to become four manuscripts that will be submitted through the appropriate channels/journals for publication.

The four different approaches are hereby presented as manuscripts for 4 papers and they are, therefore, separated and follow autonomous figure numbering and formatting.

Chapter 1 is the first paper. Here we aim to restate the problem of analysis of proteins as a problem of recognition between a few protein models using the information from a single electron. The relevant and innovative fact here is the introduction of a formal analogy with the density matrix approach to describe the missing information (e.g. the in plane orientation) in our model. It also shows the theoretical limit to our guess probability in the optimal basis and to generalization of the model to imaging with many electron.

Chapter 2 to 4 present 3 different solutions for sparse imaging problem. These solutions have relevance in optics and somehow also in electron microscopy. For completeness all have been included here whereas we decided to concentrate on the method in chapter 2 that is here specialized to the case of the protein.

We find that using the aberration that are already present and controlled in an aberration corrector we can produce a scheme of “single pixel detector” technique that especially works for the proteins.

The scheme lends itself to be adapted to a set of phase plate produced by programmable electrostatic devices as in deliverable D3.4 where there is no substantial difference.

The scheme somehow proposes the possibility to update the guess about the initial image and choose the appropriate aberration/phase shift mask in order to adapt to the guess and converge more easily. This scheme has some relevance also for the chapter 1 and the two ideas can be possibly mixed together in the actual realization.

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on diagonalization of operator through coordinate transformation (release 2)

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Q-SORT

Chapter 5 is just for the conclusions that discuss quickly the future approaches in experiments.

Annex 1 contains the referee comments

CHAPTER 1

AN EFFICIENT DISCRIMINATION OF PROTEINS IN ELECTRON MICROCOPY USING THE ORBITAL ANGULAR MOMENTUM SORTER.

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Abstract: Cryo-electron microscopy is having a huge success in solving macromolecular structure and circumventing the well-known problem of the limitation in the dose allowed per molecule. The solution is based on the use of many noisy images of individual molecules of the same kind. Instead, addressing near-atomic resolution per individual protein appears impossible as there is not enough information per the allowed dose. We address here a different optimal use of this small information. We use a measurement in a different basis to optimally distinguish between two or more specific protein models. A specific formalism based on density matrix is developed to describe the situation of an incomplete knowledge of our test model to account for example for the possible different protein orientations. The specific example of the change of basis given by the recently introduced electron Orbital Angular Momentum sorter is therefore particularly interesting and introduced in detail.

Introduction

One of the most mysterious and disturbing aspects of quantum mechanics is the dual nature of the quantum particles as both wave and localized objects. The very successful description of an electron through the complex wavefunction collides with the fact that the wavefunction is not an explicit observable for a single electron and its real ontological nature remains elusive.

In fact the process of measurement corresponds to the “collapse” of the wavefunction and a full complex wavefunction, reminiscent of the interaction it underwent, reduces to a point on a screen. All we can do is to produce a statistical inference about the wave amplitude of supposedly identical particles. Applying these concepts to the measurements of the state of the electrons in microscopy leads to the need of a large number of electrons to compose a full image of a sample [1,2].

In imaging of proteins, for example, where every electron passing through a molecule produces a damage, the loss of information connected to such measurement has pushed the challenge for novel techniques like cryo-microscopy and related statistical tomography. These techniques require the imaging of many supposedly structurally homogenous and identical proteins and the accurate imaging of a single protein is therefore largely prohibitive. And even if we got a perfect 2D image we would still need to resolve the 3D structure.

However, the recent introduction of beam shaping techniques [3,4] has changed the way electron microscopy can be applied: the concept of imaging itself needs to be changed. In particular through the use of appropriate electrostatic elements or holograms [5] it is possible to analyze the wavefunction on a different basis. The most considerable and already working case is the Orbital Angular Momentum (OAM) Sorter [6] which is inspired by light optics [7] but more general forms are now being devised in electron optics. The device uses a conformal mapping produced by two coupled phase element to induce a transformation of coordinate (Cartesian to log-polar) so that the OAM spectral decomposition of a beam can be directly measured in terms intensity on the screen.

By the time of Heisenberg, quantum mechanics can be formulated in terms of different representations that provide an identical description of the phenomena. However, in terms of measurements, a single basis is not sufficient to provide the full wavefunction including phase or even the density matrix of the state [8] .

However since this process requires a large electron statistics it is, by far, not ideal for the measurements of dose sensitive material, like proteins in aqueous solution. Since we cannot extract all information with a limited electron dose, we can instead optimize the experiment in order to extract with better efficiency only a limited information while relying on model and a prior information for the remaining part.

In the extreme case of *a priori* information, we can start from asking the analysis to distinguish between two model or hypothesis of a given object, e.g. a protein. For example, we don't know how the object will be oriented in plane and out of plane but still would like to be able to distinguish between the two different models.

The optimal measurement strategy therefore consists in finding the appropriate basis and the unitary transformation that changes the basis with two objectives: 1) hiding in the phase, that cannot be directly detected, the inessential information; 2) producing an amplitude in the new basis with a sparse character. In an extreme case, one can imagine that upon the unitary transformation the protein image were represented as a single point and that a single electron would be sufficient to recognize the protein between a few given alternatives. We shall see, based on general considerations, that a single electron based image recognition between two alternative forms is in practice impossible but we can still ask for a transformation that optimizes the recognition and produces a sparse representation of the protein.

This is a paradigm shift with respect to the simple imaging and potentially provides a very efficient alternative since information could be continuously updated while accumulating electrons and fed back into the model guessing.

Theoretical framework

We must reformulate the problem in a more formal way, in order to describe the case of the protein recognition [9]. We will assume two hypotheses concerning the protein, hereafter labeled “0” and “1”, with assigned *a priori* probabilities p_0 and p_1 . These hypotheses might correspond, for example, to the absence or presence of the protein, or to the presence of a protein in two possible conformational states. In the former case p_0 and p_1 can be deduced from the average dilution of the protein.

The electron, after its interaction with the protein, can be found either in a state $|\psi_0\rangle$ or in $|\psi_1\rangle$, depending on which of the two hypotheses applies. The problem of identifying the true hypothesis thus reduces to that of discriminating between the states $|\psi_0\rangle$ and $|\psi_1\rangle$. The discrimination strategy is based on the choice of a generalized quantum measurement performed on the electron state, with two possible outcomes $k = 0, 1$. Such a measurement is formally defined by the probability (i.e., non-negative Hermitian) operators Π_0 and $\Pi_1 = 1 - \Pi_0$. Each outcome k is associated with the electron state and leads to the choice of the hypothesis k . The outcome probability is given by $\langle \Pi_k \rangle = \text{Tr}(\rho \Pi_k)$, with $\rho = \sum_{k=0,1} p_k |\psi_k\rangle \langle \psi_k|$.

In order to rate the performance of a discrimination strategy, one needs to refer to a specific figure of merit. Hereafter we consider the guessing probability, which is given by

$$P_{guess} = p_0 \langle \psi_0 | \Pi_0 | \psi_0 \rangle + p_1 \langle \psi_1 | \Pi_1 | \psi_1 \rangle \quad (1)$$

Here, $\langle \psi_k | \Pi_k | \psi_k \rangle$ represents the probability of correctly identifying the state, provided that the k -th hypothesis applies. The first (second) term thus corresponds to the probability that the protein is in the state 0 (1) and that the measurement leads to the right identification.

This is the most natural figure of merit of a protein recognition system since its generalization to many electron permits to directly relate the dose of the protein with the recognition probability.

The typical choice of the Π operator is practically a pixel mask: if for example one uses the position in order to discriminate between the two options, the possible outcomes can be identified with a discrete set of PIXEL states $|x_i\rangle$.

The decision which positions x_i should be associated with each of the two options $\Pi_0 = \sum_{i \in I_0} |x_i\rangle \langle x_i|$, where I is the intensity of each test protein. The probability of guess for a given imaging condition is therefore given by

$$P_{guess} = \sum_{i \in \text{pixels}} \max[p_0 I_{0,i}, p_1 I_{1,i}] = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} [p_0 I_{0,i} - p_1 I_{0,i}]$$

Ideally, the k -th measurement outcome should only be possible if the electron is in the state $|\psi_k\rangle$. However, such limit can only be attained if the two states are mutually orthogonal, while a finite probability of an inconclusive result, or mistaken state identification, is always present otherwise. In the case of a projective measurement, to which we shall restrict ourselves in the following, Π_0 and Π_1 are projectors on orthogonal subspaces.

In the more general case we want to go out of the position representation and chose by unitary transformation to a basis where the P_{guess} is maximum

However, for a given pair of electron states $|\psi_0\rangle$ and $|\psi_1\rangle$. and for given *a priori* probabilities, the guessing probability cannot be arbitrarily high. In fact, one can show that P_{guess} is never higher than the so-called Helstrom bound [10]:

$$P_{guess}^{opt} = \frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{1}{4} - qp_0p_1\right)^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

Where $q = |\langle \psi_0 | \psi_1 \rangle|^2 = \int \psi_0^*(\vec{r})\psi_1(\vec{r})d\vec{r}$

Therefore, while a perfect discrimination ($P_{guess} = 1$) is always possible for $q=0$, one approaches the blind-choice case ($p_{guess} = 1/2$) as the overlap between the two states tends to 1, especially for balanced *a priori* probabilities ($p_0 \cong p_1$). The state-discrimination theory also provides the optimal measurement operators Π_0 and Π_1 , i.e. the ones that lead to a maximal guessing probability ($p_{guess} = P_{guess}^{opt}$). These are given by the projectors on the eigenstates of the operator $X = p_0|\psi_0\rangle\langle\psi_0| - p_1|\psi_1\rangle\langle\psi_1|$ corresponding to the positive and negative eigenvalues, respectively. One can easily verify that such eigenstates tend to the states $|\psi_0\rangle$ and $|\psi_1\rangle$ in the limit where their overlap tends to 0, to even and odd linear superpositions of such states when their overlap tends to 1.

The protein can be assumed to mainly affect the phase of the electron wavefunction across the transverse (x,y) plane. In fact, given an electrostatic potential $V(x, y)$ of the protein projected along the propagation direction z, the effect of the protein on the electron wavefunction is essentially given by:

$$\psi_1(x, y) = A(x, y)\exp(i\sigma V(x, y))\psi_{probe}(x, y) \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma = \frac{2\pi m_0 \gamma \lambda}{h^2}$ is a coupling constant (being m_0 the electron rest mass, γ the relativistic factor, λ the wavelength, h the Planck constant), A is the wave amplitude, and $\psi_0(x, y)$ is the wavefunction before the interaction with the sample. In a TEM experiment, an electron of the beam is prepared in a plane-wave state, corresponding to a constant $\psi_0(x, y)$ function. The electron remains in such a state in the absence of a protein (vacuum), while it transforms in the above state $\psi_1(x, y)$ if the protein is present.

In any case, the protein is made of light elements and typically produces a relatively weak phase effect ($\phi \ll \pi$ and $A=1$). This implies that the overlap between $|\psi_0\rangle$ and $|\psi_1\rangle$ is never zero, and is generally quite significant.

Notice that every unitary transformation conserves the scalar product, therefore we will never find a transformation that yields, in the new basis, separate peaks for the 2 electron states since those two peak states would be exactly orthogonal. Summarizing the perfect sorting for proteins is impossible because proteins induce small changes in the electron states and the effects they produce are not sufficiently different with each other or from the vacuum.

It is worth mentioning here a possible simplified strategy for the calculation of the projectors in eq 1 only on part Ω of the image that is considered more reliable. This leads to a less ambiguous

discrimination but at the cost of discarding a part of the data. The relation to the standard figure of merit can be calculated $P_{guess} = P(\Omega)P(guess|\Omega)$ where $P(guess|\Omega)$ is the probability to guess in the restricted part of the image. It is obvious that the overall P_{guess} undergoes the same Helstrom constrain and that in general this is disadvantageous.

In practical terms the main advantage of this particular approach is that a sparse and compact representation of the projector makes the experimental implementation easier and less prone to noise.

II. PARTIALLY MISSING INFORMATION

The scheme above is well defined but it must be modified to account for a more realistic experimental situation. In fact a desirable property of an ideal protein sorter is the capability to detect the presence of a given protein, regardless of its spatial orientation in 3D. In fact, unless *a-priori* information is given (for example by a special preparation technique) one doesn't know what the orientation of the protein is. The additional possibility is to use part of the electron dose to measure the orientation but this is somehow inefficient. Therefore, it is desirable to optimize the measurement strategy with respect to a state that is averaged on all possible orientations. Of course this ignorance of the protein state in general reduces the achievable guessing probability, i.e. the theoretical maximum P_{opt}^{guess} . On the other hand, as shown below, one can identify specific measurements that are not or much less affected by such uncertainty. And this is also another point where a unitary transformation is required.

This essentially happens if the information that is not accessible by means of such measurement corresponds to the one that is lost in the averaging procedure. In details, the classical uncertainty on the protein state is reflected in the nature of the electron state. This can no longer be written as a pure state, but rather as a statistical mixture of states:

$$\rho_k = \sum_l \wp_l |\psi_{k,l}\rangle\langle\psi_{k,l}| \quad (4)$$

This formal passage permits to use the formalism of density matrixes to describe our ignorance about the protein orientation.

Here, $|\psi_{k,l}\rangle$ is the state in which the electron transforms after the interaction with the protein, provided that this is in the l -th configuration, whose (normalized) probability is \wp_l .

In the case where the uncertainty is associated to a continuous variable, such as a rotation angle θ , the first summation in the above expression is replaced by an integral, and the discrete probability distribution \wp_l by a probability density $\wp(\theta)$.

In any case, the guessing probability reads: $P^{guess} = p_1 Tr(\rho_0 \Pi_0) + p_1 Tr(\rho_1 \Pi_1)$

III Introducing OAM and Generalized OAM sorter

The recent innovation in the measurement theory in electron microscopy has been the introduction of the OAM sorter. The use of suitable phase elements allows us to implement an angular momentum sorter, where states corresponding to different values of the orbital angular momentum are directed to different regions of the detector, and can thus be distinguished from each other. This corresponds to implementing a measurement of the orbital angular momentum L_z whose eigenvalues are $m\hbar$. It is thus useful to expand the state $|\psi_k\rangle$, into which the electron transforms after interacting with the protein in a given orientation, into its projections onto the eigenspaces of L_z :

$$|\psi_k\rangle = \sum_m \sqrt{a_m} \exp(i\alpha m) |\psi_{k,m}\rangle \quad (7)$$

This basis helps us solving one of the partial measure problem. In fact as a first step we can make a measurement that does not need the *a-priori* information about the in-plane 2D rotation. If the protein orientation around the z axis is completely unknown (i.e. the probability density $\wp(\theta)$ is flat), the state into which the electron evolves after the interaction with the protein is given by the expression in Eq. (5), with m replacing k in the pedices.

However if the orientation of the two proteins around the z axis is completely unspecified, the states become:

$$\rho_k = \sum_m a_{k,m} |\psi_{k,m}\rangle \langle \psi_{k,m}|$$

where $k = 0, 1$ and $|\psi_{k,m}\rangle$ is the projection of $|\psi_k\rangle$ on the subspace of angular momentum m.

These states are characterized by the same expectation values of L_z as the original space representation counterparts $\sigma_k = |\psi_k\rangle \langle \psi_k|$ namely $\langle \psi_k | L_z | \psi_k \rangle = \sum_M M a_{k,M}$.

However, unlike the σ_k , the states ρ_k are invariant under rotations around the z axis:

$$\exp(-i\phi L_z) \rho_k \exp(i\phi L_z) = \rho_k$$

The probability of discriminating between the two states can be obtained as a generalization of the probability in the pure state case. In fact, in each subspace of given m, one can define a two dimensional subspace spanned by the states $|\psi_{k,m}\rangle$. The overall guessing probability is given by the sum of the guessing probabilities corresponding to the different values of m, multiplied by the respective probabilities:

$$P_{guess} = \sum_m P_m P_{guess,m} \quad (4)$$

where $P_m = p_0 a_{0,m} + p_1 a_{1,m}$ and $P_{guess, M}$ is the guessing probability obtained for the qubit case after replacing the a priori probabilities p_k with $p_k a_{k,M} / (p_0 a_{0,m} + p_1 a_{1,m})$.

As a result, one obtains

$$P_{guess} = \sum_m \sum_{k=0,1} p_k a_{k,m} \langle \psi_{k,m} | \Pi_{k,m} | \psi_{k,m} \rangle \quad (5)$$

The application of the Helstrom bound to each subspace results in the overall bound:

$$P_{guess}^{opt} = \sum_m P_m P_{guess,m}^{opt} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_m (P_0 a_{0,m} + P_1 a_{1,m}) \sqrt{1 - \frac{4p_0 a_{0,m} p_1 a_{1,m} |\langle \psi_{0,m} | \psi_{1,m} \rangle|^2}{p_0 a_{0,m} + p_1 a_{1,m}}}$$

In practice the rotation about the z axis removes all the off diagonal elements of the density matrix (in the OAM part) but since the projector $\Pi_{k,m}$ act on the diagonal part the probability of guessing is not affected by the incompleteness of information. This means that while the Helstrom bound is restricted due to our ignorance the actual guess probability is unaffected leading to an actual advantage of the sorter scheme.

For comparison we will see that in a scheme based on position representation the ignorance on rotation would produce a complete inability to distinguish two protein.

The formalism with density matrix can be further use to describe an even larger ignorance about the protein to guess for example averaging the density matrix for two different out of plane orientations.

For this we must acknowledge that m is not the only quantum number since a proper basis should contain also a radial quantum number [11]. The actual density matrix is indeed only Bloch diagonal and a further averaging will reduce the content of radial information.

Realization of a generalized OAM sorter

The scheme above suggests how to build an optimal basis for the observation of the proteins. The ideal basis must necessarily be in the form $|l, m\rangle$ and therefore be eigenstate of OAM and of some radial state. Therefore it is natural to think about some generalization of the recent electron optics device called OAM sorter. The OAM sorters uses a conformal transformation to lead to the angular basis formed by OAM, indicated by the integer quantum number m , and Log-Radial momentum here simply indicated as P_ρ . As a consequence it transforms a vortex beam in a peak in the OAM space. Experimentally this is produced by two coupled phase holograms or two equivalent electrostatic phase elements.

As seen above an OAM sorter can be used to obtain an information that is independent from the actual in plane direction. However the problem can be further developed by enforcing sparsity of the representation for specific proteins. To do this, without losing the desired property of rotational invariance, we can add a specific element S3 at the end of the sorter in the plane of the OAM and P_ρ .

Fig 1. Scheme of the generalized Sorter . After the standard OAM sorter a third phase element is placed. The structure of the third element is adapted to the radial structure of the protein to be recognized.

In fact, we can add a phase element and a cylindrical lens in order to diffract only in the ρ direction. This can be obtained by an electron stigmator coupled with a round lens. The aim of this kind of process is to produce a sorter that produces a very sparse representation for the following prototype of wavefunction

$$\psi_m = R_m(\rho)\exp(im\theta)$$

Where $R_m(\rho) = \int \psi_{ew}(\rho, \theta) \exp(im\theta) d\theta$, ψ_{ew} is the aimed wavefunction after our best guess or a priori knowledge of the protein that needs to be tested. In practice, it is a vortex in the azimuthal part but it has a radial function that is fitted to the protein.

The spectrum after an ideal OAM sorter is

$$\tilde{\psi}_{EW}(p, m) = \sum \tilde{R}_m(p) \delta(m - m')$$

The way to sort these state is to use the additional phase elements to compensate for the phase of $\tilde{R}_m(p)$ and ideally obtain a diffraction after the third element in the mixed real, reciprocal space as $\tilde{\psi}_{EW}(p, m) = \sum \delta_m(\rho) \delta(m - m')$.

Notice that even if the object itself has a weak phase the phase of each $\tilde{R}_m(p)$ can vary and often does in the full range $[0, 2\pi]$ and is in general larger making the single point sorting possible for each $\tilde{R}_m(p)$ separately.

Fig 2 Example decomposition on special vortex states where the radial part is fitted on the specific protein wave. The initial protein (here we chose the side view as the decomposition does not require the n-fold symmetry) (a) is transformed in log-polar Fourier transform (b) and a single OAM value is selected (c). If the inverse process is done for each OAM we find the single vortex wave (d-g). Recomposing the first vortexes with $|\ell|$ up to 5 (h), 10 (i) and 20 (j) we find incrementally better approximation of the initial wave.

The image shows the protein “hepta pdbid 3J83” ,a heptamer of the mycobacterium tuberculosis secreted protein EspB and a detail of the log-polar spectrum. One of the OAM value is selected and isolated to give the special vortex ψ_m and back transformed to Cartesian direct coordinates to show how the single vortex looks like.

The line below shows in facts all the ψ_m for $m=1,2,3,4$. It should be noted that these vortexes are, by construction, orthogonal to each other and to the vacuum. We now assume to be able to add the correct phase element S3 in order to obtain a flat phase profile and we test if this method provides a simple way to recognize proteins.

For the test we used 3 specific protein models here indicated as Pa, Pb, Pc. Pa and Pb here selected are two different model of the protein EspB of Mycobacterium Tuberculosis. Both model refer to an heptamer but with differ in compactness: Pa based on computational modelling [12] is more loosely packed compared to Pb which is based on experimental data [13]. Pc is a completely different object still with 7-fold symmetry(“MscS channel, Ynal” [14]).

The results are tested with a S3 specific setup that selects Pa against the other models. The selection is produced by introducing a radial phase equal but opposite to that of the aimed protein. The phase “flattened” result is then diffracting very close to a single point.

The sorted results are shown in figure 3 using 2 different dose settings and the 3 different models Pa,Pb,Pc with the same 7-fold symmetry.

	Pa: Hepta pdbid 3J83	Pb: Hepta EspB	Pc:MscS channel, Ynal	Vacuum
Pa hepta pdbid 3J83	q= 1 P _{guess} = 0.5 P _{HB_inv} =0.5 P _{HB} =0.5	q= 0.99452 P _{guess} = 0.51583 P _{HB_inv} =0.53426 P _{HB} =0.55227	q= 0.99170 P _{guess} = 0.52638 P _{HB_inv} =0.55321 P _{HB} =0.56427	q= 0.99111 P _{guess} = 0.53347 P _{HB_inv} =0.55845 P _{HB} =0.56653
Pb Hepta EspB	q= 0.99452 P _{guess} = 0.51583 P _{HB_inv} =0.53426 P _{HB} =0.55227	q= 1 P _{guess} = 0.5 P _{HB_inv} =0.5 P _{HB} =0.5	q=0.9969 P _{guess} = 0.51692 P _{HB_inv} =0.52893 P _{HB} =0.53919	q= 0.99552 P _{guess} = 0.52515 P _{HB_inv} =0.54194 P _{HB} =0.54726
Pc MscS channel, Ynal	q= 0.99170 P _{guess} = 0.52638 P _{HB_inv} =0.55321 P _{HB} =0.56427	q= 0.9969 P _{guess} = 0.51692 P _{HB_inv} =0.52893 P _{HB} =0.53919	q=1 P _{guess} = 0.5 P _{HB_inv} =0.5 P _{HB} =0.5	q= 0.99763 P _{guess} = 0.50974 P _{HB_inv} =0.52993 P _{HB} =0.53437
Vacuum	q= 0.99111 P _{guess} = 0.53347 P _{HB_inv} =0.55845 P _{HB} =0.56653	q= 0.99552 P _{guess} = 0.52515 P _{HB_inv} =0.54194 P _{HB} =0.54726	q= 0.99763 P _{guess} = 0.50974 P _{HB_inv} =0.52993 P _{HB} =0.53437	q= 1 P _{guess} = 0.5 P _{HB_inv} =0.5 P _{HB} =0.5

Table 1 Table of the probability of guess in OAM basis between 3 different proteins and vacuum. For each couple we indicated the scalar product q, the guess probability in the log-polar Fourier basis

(OAM) the Helstrom bound for the guess probability if the rotation information is averaged $P_{\text{HB_inv}}$ and if not P_{HB} .

It is interesting to notice that limiting to the area Ω where $m \neq 0$ and p is close to zero $P(\text{guess}|\Omega)$ approaches 96% in all cases. Whereas this is not determining the overall merit factor this is useful to more easily devise the easiest guess strategy.

In general for a reliable guess of the protein we will then need more than 1 electron. The ingredients are the probability $P(0|0)$ and $P(1|1)$ namely the probability that outcome of our single electron measurement is 0 (or 1) if the actual protein is zero (or 1). But assuming these two values are similar we can just think in terms of probability of guessing in both cases and make a binomial distribution.

The binomial can be further approximated with a normal distribution. The dose necessary to a guess with, say, 99% confidence is given by using a normal probability distribution $\mathfrak{N}\left(p, \sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{N}}\right)$ and the 3σ criterion $\frac{p-0.5}{\sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{N}}} > 3$. This gives the necessary number of electron N that can be normalized to the illuminated area to give the dose. For a single electron probability of $P_{\text{guess}}=0.52$ this corresponds to a dose of $0.2e/\text{\AA}^2$.

Since the probability have this order of magnitude we simulated the low dose sorter images in fig 3.

It is easy to appreciate that when the protein is the right one a series of peaks are visible even with only $1e/\text{\AA}^2$. Conversely even with large dose the analysis of the protein in the wrong direction gives only noise. So even with the low dose the results are sufficient to discriminate the two cases.

Fig 3 Example of recognition of 3 proteins Pa, Pb, Pc with 7 fold symmetry using (a-c) $10e^-/\text{\AA}^2$ and (d-f) $1e^-/\text{\AA}^2$. The sorter 3 has been tuned on the first protein that indeed shows a distinctive peak in a, d, all other proteins show only minor intensity peaks. Even in the low dose experiment the protein can be recognized.

For sake of comparison we reported also the maximum probability of guess for the 3 protein above showing that the probabilities are never very different from 50% that is the complete ignorance.

Conclusions

In this work we have calculated the possibility to distinguish between two hypothesis of proteins per each single electron measurement. The maximum sorting ability remains anyway limited to the Helstrom bound that is a strong limitation considering the large wave overlap of the wavefunction for electron passing through different proteins. A more generalized formalism uses the similarity to mixed states in QM and uses density matrixes permits to introduce uncertainty of the two test proteins regarding, for example, the ignorance about the protein orientation. A smart choice of the basis permits to eliminate the problem related to this missing information. The most conspicuous example is the case of the OAM basis that permits to eliminate the in plane rotation information from the recognition problem. A new device based on a generalization of the OAM sorter is here presented permitting a very good discrimination even with a minimal dose of $1e^-/\text{\AA}^2$.

For the future the use of correlated electrons should allow for a strong increase of the guess probability with schemes like multipass or entangled electrons that permit to overcome the limitations imposed by the small phase difference.

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CHAPTER 2

USING ABERRATIONS TO BEAT THE DIFFRACTION LIMIT

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(Dated: September 14, 2018)

One form of computational imaging relies upon a projected sequence of different illumination patterns and a measurement of the backscattered light associated with each to reconstruct an image estimate of the unknown object. The frequently cited advantage of such an approach is that the detector array that would normally be placed in the image plane of the camera can be substituted with a single element (pixel) detector and hence access wavelengths where detector arrays are either unobtainable or very costly. This form of computational imaging, based on sequences of projected pattern sequences is called a “single-pixel camera” or “computational ghost imager”. What we show in this work is that by appropriate choice of illumination patterns the resolution of the reconstructed image can exceed the diffraction limit. Specifically rather than compensating for aberrations, we introduce time varying aberrations in the form of Zernike polynomials to create complicated point spread functions with super oscillatory spatial features and it is these features that allow us to recover spatial information beyond the diffraction limit. Compared to a simple, aberration-free imaging system based on a scanning a diffraction-limited spot, we show that by deliberately introducing excess aberrations we can double the lateral resolution. Such a technique is applicable to any imaging system based upon projected light where the aberrations are understood and controllable and could for example be implemented using spatial light modulators, deformable mirrors or even potentially with electron beams using aberration control.

Single-pixel cameras use a programmable mask to either project an illumination pattern or filter the backscattered light to measure the overlap between the mask pattern and the object scene [1]. This overlap is measured using a single element (pixel) detector large enough to integrate over the entire field of view. By employing a known sequence of masks it is possible to reconstruct an estimate of the entire image. The potential of this approach lies in two aspects, firstly that single-pixel detectors are available at wavelengths where the detector arrays for normal cameras are not [2]. Secondly, that by appropriate choice of masks and prior assumptions about image properties then the number of masks required to obtain a good estimate of the image can be far fewer than the number of pixels in the image – an example of compressed sensing.

The choice of mask patterns is central to the performance of the system and the required algorithms used to reconstruct the image. One popular choice are masks derived from Hadamard matrices where each mask probes a subset of spatial frequencies, These masks are orthogonal which simplifies the reconstruction algorithm that can be as simple the additional of all the mask patterns used, each weighted by the magnitude of the overlap signal recorded by the single-pixel detector. If the mask

patterns are orthogonal with respect to each other then the number of masks and corresponding required is exactly equal to the number of pixels in the image. However, if one is willing to apply constraints to the reconstruction, e.g. that the image is sparse in its spatial frequencies then, as stated above, it is possible to reconstruct a high quality measurement from a significantly smaller number of mask patterns and measurements.

If the mask patterns are implemented using a pixelated spatial light modulator then specifying their design to be orthogonal is straightforward (e.g. Hadamard, or similar). If, however, the patterns are produced in other ways, e.g. using natural scattering, then orthogonality between the patterns can no longer be enforced and the reconstruction algorithm becomes more complicated. One approach to solving this non orthogonally relies upon traditional Matrix inversion, but since the size of the matrix is very large (number of elements \approx number of pixels²) then this inversion is, at best, computationally intensive and more generally difficult to constrain based upon assumptions about the image. Here we report an alternative approach that is computationally trivial and hence updateable on a pattern by pattern.

If the patterns are described by p_i and the measured overlap signals are ms_i then a traditional reconstruction algorithm for the image I_N from N mask patterns is given by[3,4]

$$I_N = \sum_{i=1}^N (ms_i - \langle ms \rangle) p_i. \quad (1)$$

We call this algorithm “traditional ghost imaging, (TGI)”

If the patterns are not orthogonal then this algorithm fails since the non-orthogonal components, i.e. overlapping parts of p_i , are overly emphasized in the image reconstruction.

An alternative algorithm can be devised which iterates towards an image reconstruction based on the current estimate modified by the new pattern and signal. Key to this algorithm the ability to predict the signal that would be obtained from any pattern under the assumption that the previously calculated image was complete. This predicted signal, based on an image estimate I_j , is given as $ps(I_j)$. The iterative reconstruction of the image from a sequence of applied patterns is then given as

$$I_i = I_{i-1} + [(ms_i - \langle ms \rangle) - (ps(I_{i-1}) - \langle ps \rangle)]p_i, \quad (2)$$

where $\langle \dots \rangle$ denotes the average value and $I_0 = 0$.

We call this algorithm “orthogonalised ghost imaging, (OGI).”

Note that care needs to be taken such that both the measured and predicted are correctly scaled such that as the reconstructed images approaches the true image that the quantity $[(ms_i - \langle ms \rangle) - (ps(I_{i-1}) - \langle ps \rangle)]$ tends to zero. One approach to ensuring this scaling is to iteratively normalize the signals such that $\langle ps \rangle = \langle ms \rangle$ and $\sigma_{ps} = \sigma_{ms}$.

In this work we adopt a random weighting of Zernike polynomials, to produce random aberration and hence a sequence of highly distorted point spread functions in the far field. Using the first four orders of Zernike polynomials (tip/tilt, astigmatism/defocus, trefoil/coma and quatrefoil/secondary astigmatism/spherical aberration), see figure 1, multiplied to give several wavelengths of aberration we can calculate the far-field point spread functions, see figure 2.

Figure 1 - The 14 the lowest order Zernike polynomials, depicted in terms of their phase profile where the grey scale ranges denotes $0-2\pi$. (first row, tip/tilt; second row astigmatism/defocus, third row, trefoil/coma and forth row, quatrefoil/secondary astigmatism/spherical aberration).

We take these calculated point spread functions as the pattern sequence, p_i with which to illuminate the object and then model the backscattered signal in terms of the correlation between the pattern and the object, which we take as the measured signal, s_i . We then take these modelled signals and calculated the anticipated reconstructed image as obtain from equation 1 and equation 2.

For the purpose of our numerical model we assume a 4mm diameter beam illuminating a 10mm sized spatial light modulator, programed to apply the random aberrations. The aberrated beam is then propagated using plane-wave decomposition to a focusing lens of 2m focal length with the test object placed in the back focal plane of this lens. The backscattered signal is calculated as being in proportion to the overlap between this object and the aberrated beam.

Figure 2 - Random combinations of Zernike aberrations (top) and the corresponding calculated far-field point spread functions (bottom).

Figure 3 - Reconstruction based upon 10,000 patterns like those in figure 2 using both the TGI and OGI algorithms, calculated on a 512x512 array.

Figure 3 shows the reconstructed images obtained after 10,000 Zernike aberration patterns using both traditional and orthogonal ghost imaging reconstruction algorithms. By analysing the depth of the reconstructed intensity modulation as a function of radius from the centre (normalised to the peak modulation) figure 4 shows that the resolution of the OGI images is approximately twice that of the TGI image. We note also that the corrective nature of the algorithm has also flattened the modulation transfer function to give a more equal response to a wider range of spatial frequencies.

Figure 4 - The intensity modulation depth as a function of radius for images obtained using 10,000 Zernike random aberrations and reconstructed using both TGI and OGI.

Rather than comparing TGI to OGI a more interesting comparison can be made to the images that can be obtained by simply removing all aberrations other than tip/tilt, to give a randomly scanning diffraction limited spot. Figure 5 shows the reconstructed images obtained after 10,000 randomly positioned diffraction-limited spots using both traditional and orthogonal ghost imaging reconstruction algorithms. By analysing the depth of the reconstructed intensity modulation as a function of radius from the centre (normalized to the peak modulation) figure 6 shows that the resolution of the OGI images is equivalent to that of the TGI image. More significantly neither of the reconstruction algorithms using data acquired from the scanning spot match the resolution of the image produced

Figure 5 - Reconstructions based upon 10,000 randomly positioned diffraction limited spots using both the TGI and OGI algorithms, calculated on a 512x512 array.

using OGI using the patterns derived from the Zernike aberrations.

Having established that the addition of aberrations can improve

the imaging performance of a scanning beam system we also chose to apply the approach to a real work object and compare the images obtained to that that could have been obtained by simple raster scanning. For our comparison we chose a section of a protein, in part because our intended application is within cryo-EM. Figure 7 shows the full protein, the protein section and comparison between the raster scanned and aberration scanned images. The scaling of the images was chosen such that the feature size was at the limit of what could be imaged using a diffraction limited raster scan. We see clearly from the images and the recovered features the clear advantage of aberration scanning.

Figure 6 - The intensity modulation depth as a function of radius for images obtained using 10,000 randomly position diffraction limited spots, reconstructed using both TGI and OGI.

These results seem to indicate that a computational imaging system based upon the projection of a sequence of randomly derived, but known, heavy aberrated spots can improve upon the diffraction limited image that could have been obtained from a scanning, diffraction-limited but none aberrated spots. The physical origin of this improvement lies in the super oscillatory spatial features of the aberrated point spread functions

Figure 7 - The full protein (a), the highlighted section 9b) and the raster scanned (c) and aberration scanned (d) images.

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CHAPTER 3

SINGLE-PIXEL IMAGING USING CAUSTIC PATTERNS

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ABSTRACT

Single-pixel imaging uses a time-varying transmission mask placed in the illumination to achieve imaging without the use of detector arrays. While most research in this field uses sophisticated masks implemented using spatial light modulators, such methods are not available at all length scales and wavelengths of illumination. Here we show that alternatively a sequence of projected caustic intensity patterns can be used as the basis for the single-pixel imaging of objects. Caustics are formed as a consequence of slowly varying random phase masks, such as for example the surface of a swimming pool, which potential makes caustics an option at a range of length scales and wavelengths.

Introduction

Single-pixel cameras are a form of computational imaging where a time-varying mask is used to create projected patterns to illuminate an object and a single-pixel detector to measure the total time-varying intensity of the back-scattered light³. Equivalently the object can be illuminated full-field and the time varying mask be inserted prior to the detector. In both configurations, the signals from the detector are a measure of the overlap between the mask pattern with the object and, as pioneered by Baraniuk and co-workers, given many such measurements corresponding to different patterns it is possible to reconstruct an image of the object². One advantage of such single-pixel approaches is that they negate the need for detector arrays, which can be prohibitively expensive at some operating wavelengths.

Much of the research in the area of single-pixels cameras has been directed towards the choice/design of mask patterns and the algorithms needed to reconstruct the image from these patterns and detector data³. The choice of patterns ranges from those based upon random laser speckle⁴, to those implemented using spatial light modulators capable of creating complicated masks at very high refresh rates, including both Hadamard⁵ and more bespoke patterns aimed at optimising specific scenarios⁶. However, the use of a spatial light modulator sets a limitation upon the operating wavelengths, requiring sophisticated solutions at any wavelength much removed from the visible spectrum⁷.

Rather than using designed patterns, the use of laser speckle patterns makes possible the application of a wide variety of random processes for the generation of the illumination patterns, but still leaves the problem of needing to know the precise spatial form of the pattern produced^{8,9}. Measuring these patterns with a detector array or other imaging system would largely negate the operational advantage of the single-pixel approach, hence the form of the pattern needs to be predicted from knowledge of the process producing it. This prediction might be direct from knowledge of a transmission mask imaged to the plane of the object or from knowledge of the mask and the subsequent computational propagation of the light to the object plane. As an alternative to speckle, which can be difficult to predict, in this work we consider the use of caustic patterns that are generated whenever light is reflected or transmitted through a slowly varying phase mask¹⁰ (for example the patterns formed on the bottom of a swimming pool, resulting from the imperfect focusing of the sunlight by the ripples on the surface of the water). Although these slowly varying phase masks still produce random speckle patterns in the far-field, predictable caustics are produced at a characteristic propagation distance, with the transition between the two having been studied previously¹¹. Using caustics for single-pixel imaging has also been postulated previously, but in that work did not yield recognisable images¹².

In this work, we perform a proof of principle single-pixel imaging using caustic patterns, which although we create using a programmable spatial light modulator (SLM), at other wavelengths could be implemented with other systems. One possible alternative would be the use of deformable mirrors which are reflective over an extended wavelength range and can create smoothly varying height profiles that will give rise to caustics in the reflected light after propagation.

The use of projected patterns for single-pixel imaging should not be confused with the use of projected patterns in structured light microscopy, the latter of which combines structured illumination (including speckle) with conventional spatially resolved imaging to achieve sub Rayleigh resolution¹³.

Figure 1. Experimental realisation. The output from a HeNe laser is magnified and spatially filtered using a 50 mm focal length lens (L1), a 50 μm precision pin-hole (P) and a 400 mm focal

length lens (L2). A Cambridge Correlators liquid-crystals SLM (model: SDE1024) is used to impart the caustics hologram onto the incoming collimated beam. The first diffracted order is selected by an aperture (A) placed in the far-field of a 250 mm focal length lens (L3). A 500 mm focal length lens (L4) is used in conjunction to L3 to magnify the caustic patterns. The plane of the SLM and the plane of the virtual modulator are highlighted by the blue-dotted lines. A ground-glass plate (GGP) is used to scatter the light ensuring that the single-pixel detector (Thorlabs photo-multiplier tube (PMT), model PMM01) collects light from all regions of the object. The object (Obj.) can be placed at some distance d from the image plane of the SLM, corresponding to a distance d' from the magnified plane of the virtual modulator. In order to verify that the experimentally generated caustic patterns matched the modelled ones, a camera (Canon EOS 5D Mark III) was placed with its sensor array directly in the plane of the object.

Results and analysis

As shown in the experimental arrangement in Fig.1, the output beam from a HeNe laser is collimated and expanded to fill the aperture of a spatial light modulator. This modulator is programmed to display a smoothly varying random phase mask that is fully within the 0 to 2π range. The scale of these phase fluctuations is such that the light is approximately focused to a few 100 mm after the plane of the modulator (c.f. the bottom of a swimming pool). To ensure the fidelity of the phase fluctuations, the modulator is used in diffractive mode where the addition of a phase-grating to the phase mask produces the desired complex beam in the first diffracted order, which is selected in the far-field of the modulator using an aperture, and then re-imaged to create a virtual modulator at some other plane. The object is then placed at the required distance after the plane of this virtual modulator. The overlap between the object and the caustic pattern is measured in transmission using a large area photomultiplier. A ground-glass diffuser (1500 grit) inserted between the object and the detector prevents the finite diameter of the detector vignetting the image. The objects used in this publication consist of 10 mm 10 mm laser printed acetate sheets.

The spatial form of the projected caustic patterns at some distance from the plane of the SLM can be modelled from the knowledge of the phase masks displayed on the SLM using a plane-wave decomposition. Additionally, it is possible to verify that the measured caustic patterns are the same as the modelled ones, by replacing the object with a camera (we used a lensless Canon EOS 5D Mark III, due to its large chip). The random phase mask is calculated by assigning every pixel a random value and then applying a spatial low-pass filter to obtain a slowly varying random pattern which can then be rescaled to lie in the

0 to 2π range and display on the modulator. Figure 2 shows examples of the phase masks applied (a), the corresponding phase mask displayed on the SLM with an added grating (b). The distance d from the plane of the SLM corresponds to the distance d' from the magnified plane of the virtual modulator. Since d' depends on the somewhat arbitrary choice of lenses used to relay the plane of the SLM, here we mention d instead (i.e. as if the object was placed directly after the SLM).

The scale and depth of the phase fluctuations were such that the caustics were formed at a distance $d = 9.5$ cm from the plane of the SLM. The object was placed to intercept the caustic patterns at both the characteristic distance (i.e. $d = 9.5$ cm) and at two other distances of 3 cm and 15 cm. Knowing the spatial form of the phase fluctuations allows the accurate form of the caustics at

three distances from the plane of the virtual modulator to be predicted and these can be seen in (c), (e), and (g), whereas the measured caustics by means of a camera are shown in (d), (f), and (h). We note that the agreement between the

Figure 2. Generated caustic patterns using a liquid-crystals SLM. A phase mask (a) is used to generate a hologram (b) that is displayed on the SLM. A numerical model is used to model the intensity patterns at three increasing distances from the image plane of the SLM (3, 9.5 and 15 cm) showing a transition from caustic to speckle. The modelled intensity patterns are shown in (c), (e), and (g) whereas the intensity patterns, as recorded by a camera, are shown in (d), (f), and (h). The distance d between the camera plane and the plane of the SLM for each pattern is reported at the bottom.

Modelled and measured caustic patterns is high. Moreover, as the distance is increased beyond the designed 9.5 cm, the spatial form of the projected caustics tends towards a speckle pattern, as visible in (g) and (h).

Using a sequence of $i = 1 \dots N$ random caustic patterns to illuminate the object and measuring the single-pixel signal allows the image to be reconstructed using standard single-pixel camera algorithms. If the caustic patterns are described by $p_i(x, y)$ and the corresponding measured signal from the single-pixel detector are s_i , then a traditional reconstruction algorithm for the image I from N mask patterns is ^{8,14} :

$$I = \sum_{i=1}^N (s_i - \bar{s}_i) p_i(x, y) \quad (1)$$

where s_i is the average value of all the single-pixel detector signals.

In this work we have not used complicated image reconstruction protocols or image post-processing, since we aim to establish the basic principles from which recognisable images are obtained without recourse to sophisticated denoising algorithms or image priors. The only alteration made to the basic algorithm described in equation 1 is limiting the average signal s_i to only include the most recent 100 measurements so as to reduce the effect of detector drift on the reconstruction.

Images of an eight-spokes Siemens resolution-target are shown in Fig.3, reconstructed using modelled caustics and modelled signals (a), as well as modelled caustics and measured signals (b). As anticipated the two types of reconstructed images are highly similar, confirming the accuracy of the modelled patterns. Caustic patterns as detected at 9.5 cm from the plane of the SLM (Fig.2(a) and (b)) were used for these reconstructions.

The radial contrast functions (red- and green-series) shown in Fig.3(c) were extracted from the pixel intensity values of the reconstructed images of the Siemens-star resolution target shown in Fig.3(a) and (b). The low and high spatial-frequency limits (labelled LF and HF respectively) were defined using the $1/e^2$ criterion as applied to radial contrast. The power-spectrum computed for a large number of modelled caustic patterns at 9.5 cm from the plane of the SLM is also shown (black-series). We note that the bandpass like nature in the spatial-frequency domain of the power spectrum are mirrored by the computed radial contrast functions indicating the range of spatial frequencies accessible for imaging with caustic patterns.

Figure 4 shows the reconstruction of images where an object (shown in the inset (d)) is placed at several distances from the

Figure 3. Radial contrast functions and power spectrum. The images of a Siemens resolution-target (shown in the inset (d)) were reconstructed using the modelled patterns and modelled signals (as shown in (a)), and using the modelled patterns and measured signals (as shown in (b)). The corresponding radial contrast functions are shown by the red and green series in (c). The black-series represents the DC-subtracted power spectrum of the modelled caustic patterns, as detected at 9.5 cm from the plane of the SLM. As to be expected, the extent of the power spectrum in the spatial-frequency domain agrees with the computed radial contrast function and shows the available range of spatial frequencies in an ideal case. The low and high spatial frequencies are marked at the $1/e^2$ amplitude shown by the dotted blue-series and labelled LF and HF respectively.

SLM (3, 9.5 and 15cm for a-c respectively), but the caustic patterns are only modelled for the target distance of 9.5cm. In each case the reconstruction was based on a set of 30,000 caustics. One notes that the distance between the SLM and the object is not critical, however, the the image quality is best when the propagating distance of the modelled caustic patterns matches the distance between the object and the SLM.

Figure 5 shows the reconstruction of the same object as in the previous figure with different numbers of caustics used in the reconstruction, specifically 3,000, 10,000 and 30,000 for a-c respectively. In all three cases the object was located at the target distance of 9.5 cm, corresponding to the plane where the caustics patterns were modelled. While a reasonable reconstruction is obtained for 10,000 patterns with only minor improvement when going up to 30,000, the outlines of the object are already well defined when only 3,000 caustics have been used.

Figure 4. Reconstructed images with a 768x768 resolution of a general binary object using caustic patterns as measured at various distances from the plane of the SLM. The object shown in (d) was reconstructed using the PMT signals measured at 3, 9.5, and 15 cm from the plane of the SLM, producing the images shown in (a-c) respectively. In each case the caustic patterns were calculated for a distance of 9.5 cm.

Figure 5. Reconstructed images with a 768x768 resolution of a general binary object using different numbers of caustic patterns to sample the object. The object shown in (d) was reconstructed using the PMT signals measured with 3,000, 10,000 and 30,000 different caustic patterns, producing the images shown in (a-c) respectively.

As is expected for a single-pixel approach, the smallest feature size reconstructed in the image corresponds to the smallest feature size of the projected patterns. However, as apparent Fig.3(ab) another interesting feature of these images is that the low spatial-frequencies are poorly reproduced

in the reconstructed images, effectively resulting in an edge-enhancing band-pass filter in the spatial domain, in accordance to the radial contrast function and power spectrum plotted in Fig.3(c).

Conclusions

In this work we have shown that a sequence of projected caustic intensity patterns can be used as the basis for single-pixel imaging of objects, albeit images which are inherently edge-enhanced. Since caustic patterns are a natural consequence of smoothly varying random phase masks the principle could be applied to a wide range of possible wavelengths, wave types, and various implementations of phase masks. For example, caustics are formed by the refraction of light by ocean waves and hence could be used to perform imaging of submerged objects. However, note that in this case the surface profile of the water would also have to be known so that the spatial form of the resulting caustics could be calculated and used within the reconstruction algorithm.

The data in support of this publication (i.e. the measured signals from the PMT and a caustic patterns generator) is available at the following repository¹⁵.

Acknowledgements

E.T. acknowledges the financial support from the EPSRC Centre for Doctoral Training in Intelligent Sensing and Measurement (EP/L016753/1). All authors acknowledge the support from ERC TWISTS (192382), and H2020, Q-sort (project ID: 766970).

Author contributions statement

The original concept for this work was derived by E.T and M.P. and refined by all authors. The computer modelling was undertaken by M.P., B.S. and D.S. The apparatus was constructed by E.T and B.S. with additional input from D.S. All authors contributed to the writing of the manuscript.

Additional information

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this article.

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CHAPTER 4

TIME OF FLIGHT 3D IMAGING THROUGH MULTIMODE FIBERS

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Traditional endoscopes use bundles of optical fibres to relay each pixel of an image from facet to facet. Alternatively, by treating a single, multi-mode, fibre as a complex aberration and applying corrective beam shaping it is possible to relay an image along the fibre length. Here we show that by appropriate beam-shaping we can relay an image from the far-field of the fibre entrance facet, and by using pulsed illumination with time-resolved detection, achieve 3D imaging through a single optical fibre. We demonstrate imaging up to 1m from the fibre with a lateral resolution of 59x59 pixels and a depth resolution of 1.5mm. Such minimally invasive endoscopic 3D imaging has applications in minimally invasive healthcare, remote inspection and security regimes.

Introduction

Multimode optical fibres (MMFs) form the densest possible way of transporting information using light. This fact makes them ideal candidates to be employed as endoscopes, as they guarantee the smallest possible intrusion for a given spatial resolution of a retrieved image. However, this density of information is made possible by employing the full set of propagating fibre modes, and as result any input light that is not a pure fibre mode gets unrecognisably scrambled through group velocity dispersion and modal crosstalk upon propagation through the MMF, leading to speckle patterns at the output. Until recently this presented a hurdle that made the retrieval of images of scenes from beyond a MMF unrealistic.

Still, as long as a MMF remains unperturbed the nature of the scrambling processes involved is almost entirely linear and static. In other words, a given input will always reproduce the same output, and therefore the fibre can in principle be approximated to a high degree of accuracy by a single so called transmission matrix (TM). If this TM is known for a given MMF, it can be effectively be used as a key to recover an image from the speckle. But both the size of this matrix as well as the number of potential pixels in a retrieved image is given by the number of supported modes in the MMF. As such, only with the advent of high speed wavefront shaping through spatial light modulators (SLMs) and their binary counterparts digital micromirror devices (DMDs) has it actually become feasible to, in a reasonable time frame, determine the full TM for a MMF of sufficient size to be interesting for imaging.

Several research groups have recently used the capability to measure a TM to achieve imaging in a variety of ways. This has for example been done implicitly using machine learning, where a computer

learns to recognise the images projected on the fibre input from their resulting speckle patterns. Explicitly it has both been shown to work using a uniformly illuminated scene where the TM is used to decompose the measured speckle pattern into known modes that can be transformed to a spatial image, or conversely by using the TM to control illumination through the MMF itself to effectively raster scan a target object. The latter method in particular has recently been used for in vivo imaging of life mouse brains as a clear demonstration of the potential of MMFs as endoscopes. In all cases however, the object being imaged was either very close to the fibre or being projected onto the fibre.

In this work we measure the TM of an MMF as well as the further propagation from the fibre output into the far field, using a sub-ns pulsed laser source. We subsequently use the measured TM to reconstruct an array of spots in the far field of the fibre distal end to raster scan across a scene. With a second MMF as a collection aperture for backscattered light, we measured the time of flight as well as the associated reflectivity of each spot. With this combined system of two multimode optical fibres we show that we can achieve 3D images of macroscopic scenes up to a metre beyond their distal ends, with no further optics required at the output.

Choice of fibre

The primary source of the scrambling of light propagating through multimode fibres is modal dispersion. Light can only propagate through a multimode fibre in a fixed set of modes determined by the fibre core diameter and the refractive index difference between core and cladding, the latter of which can be summarised by the numerical aperture (NA) of the fibre. These modes cover a range of different wavevectors and therefore acquire a range of different phases upon propagation from one end of the fibre to the other. Most of the scrambling therefore stems solely from the decomposition of an input light field into a subsection of these modes, which then quickly develop a chaotic set of phase differences and therefore collectively form a speckle interference pattern. A secondary contribution to the scrambling stems from the coupling between neighbouring modes due to the MMF typically not being a perfect cylinder, which becomes a more or less significant factor depending on how severely perturbed the fibre is.

This modal dispersion based scrambling is one of the reasons why the TM method works so well for MMFs, but it also exacerbates a problem. Namely that the set of possible modes is dependent on the frequency of the light, and therefore a measured TM is only valid for a very specific frequency. Most of the work in the field is therefore done with very narrow line width, or long coherence length, lasers. However, as we want to include time of flight in our measurements we require the use of a pulsed laser, which necessarily restricts the coherence length. For the TM method to be valid for our purposes all modes need to be able to interfere with a high degree of visibility at the distal end of the fibre, i.e. their optical path lengths need to be sufficiently similar. To determine a minimal condition where this is true, it suffices to look at the optical path length difference between the shortest and longest possible optical path lengths, or the lowest and highest order fibre modes. These can be approximated geometrically as

$$z_{low} = nL, \quad (1)$$

and

$$z_{high} = \frac{z_{low}}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{NA}{n}\right)^2}}, \quad (2)$$

where n is the refractive index of the fibre core, L is the physical length of the fibre, and NA the numerical aperture. The difference between these values should be far shorter than the coherence length of the laser used in the fibre, $L_{coh} = c\Delta t/n$, where Δt is the pulse length. Combining the above leaves

$$nL \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{NA}{n}\right)^2}} - 1 \right) \ll \frac{c\Delta t}{n}. \quad (4)$$

For a standard step-index multimode fibre as used in this work with a core refractive index of ~ 1.46 at visible wavelengths, and a corresponding numerical aperture of ~ 0.22 , this reduces to approximately $L \ll 40c\Delta t$.

Figure 1- Schematic of the experimental setup. f_1 (120mm lens), a_1 (30 μ m aperture) and f_2 (300mm lens) form a spatial filter and beam expander to illuminate the DMD with an \sim 1cm diameter collimated beam at 24 $^\circ$ from the normal of the DMD surface. The brightest diffraction order is then converted to circular polarisation by a linear polariser and quarter waveplate. f_3 (400mm lens) is placed at f after the DMD in that arm, with a_2 (iris) placed in the Fourier plane to filter out only the first order. f_4 (80mm lens) and f_5 (40x objective) act as a telescope to project this plane onto the input facet of MMF₁ (50 μ m core, 0.22 NA, 20cm long, f_c /pc coupled patch cable.) The other end of the multimode fibre is aimed at a screen 20cm away for the characterisation step, or a general scene for the imaging. The CCD camera images this screen for the characterisation step, triggering the DMD to switch frames after capturing an image while the camera itself is triggered by pd_1 , a reference photodiode directly after the laser. During the imaging step the reflected light is instead sampled by MMF₂ (500 μ m core, 0.22 NA, 20cm long, SMA coupled patch cable), the close end of which is put into direct contact with a fast APD with a square detector area of 500 μ m on a side. The signal from this APD is fed into a high speed digitiser, along with a reference signal from pd_2 (high speed photodiode) which is placed just after a_3 (iris) in the Fourier plane of the DMD in the corresponding negative diffraction arm.

At the same time, the depth resolution of a time of flight based imaging system is closely influenced by the pulse length as well, and in principle a shorter pulse length would provide a higher axial resolution. There is therefore a fundamental trade off between fibre length (and NA) on the one hand, and depth resolution on the other. In practice, however, the primary limiting factor for pulse length and therefore depth resolution tends to be the sampling rate of the digitiser used to measure the returning pulse.

For the work presented here we had access to a high speed digitiser with a sampling rate of 2.5GHz, corresponding to time bins of 0.4ns. We chose to use a 7.5kHz Q-switched 532nm laser with a pulse length of ~ 0.67 ns to complement it. From equation 4 this implies that our MMF should be much shorter than approximately 8 metres. To verify this we tested the accuracy of measured TMs of several $50\mu\text{m}$ core diameter, 0.22 NA step-index fibres ranging from 1cm up to 50cm long, which showed no significant degradation with added fibre length. For all further results presented here we used a 20cm long step-index fibre with a NA of 0.22 and a core diameter of $50\mu\text{m}$, comfortably fulfilling the above criterion.

Figure 2 - Example images of the intensity patterns in the far field ($Z = 20\text{cm}$) of the output of the illuminating fibre. a) A spot formed in the far field after correcting using the measured transmission matrix; b) same as a, plotted on a log scale to show the background speckle that remains; c) a speckle pattern as typically observed when not correcting for the transmission matrix; d) a map of the efficiencies of the corrections, measured by taking images as in a and dividing the intensity in a 5×5 pixel box around the spot by the total intensity in the image, as a function of output angle of the spot.

Fibre characterisation

Achieving imaging through multimode fibres with the transmission matrix method requires several steps. The first of which is measuring the actual transmission matrix. We mostly follow the plane wave method with an internal reference as previously described by Tomas Cizmar's group. The experimental setup used is illustrated in figure 1. This method involves placing a digital micromirror device (DMD) in the Fourier plane of the input facet of a MMF, suitably magnified to make optimal use of the full face of the DMD. The fibre is then characterised by scanning a regular grid of angled plane waves at the DMD, i.e. a set of linear gratings with varying k_x and k_y , which corresponds to scanning a focal spot across a regular grid at the fibre facet. At any one time a superposition of two such plane waves are displayed, one of which is kept fixed as the internal reference throughout the characterisation step. At the same time the resultant speckle pattern at the output of the fibre is imaged, an example of which is shown in figure 2c. By varying the phase of the internal reference for each probe plane wave this method allows the retrieval of both the amplitude and the phase contribution to the TM from that sample plane wave for each spatial coordinate on the camera.

Figure 3 - Example of measured time of flight histogram after averaging over 500 laser pulses, corresponding to a pixel on the head of the dinosaur figurine in figure ... Shown are the raw measured data (blue), the data after correction for the expected $1/t^2$ signal decay (red), and the fully processed histogram (yellow) after postprocessing as described in the text: a Gaussian convolution with neighbouring pixels; a five fold spline interpolation; and a correction for an overall average background signal. The dotted black line indicates the position of the time of flight ultimately assigned to this pixel, and the associated reflectivity is found by summing over the indicated area.

The major adjustment we made to this system is the plane at which we image the speckle pattern, namely about 20cm beyond the distal end of the MMF. At this plane we place a white screen, which we image onto a CCD. This implies that the transmission matrix we measure is not a pure fibre TM, but in fact already includes the desired propagation into the far field. Each row of the TM therefore corresponds to the relative amplitude and phase differences acquired by the set of modes probed as seen at a single position in the far field at the distal end of the fibre. To reconstruct a focal spot at a given position we then sum the probe plane waves at the DMD with the phase offsets read out from the corresponding row of the TM. This is a mathematically straightforward but computationally intensive problem that we solve using a GPU (Nvidia GTX1080Ti). A full matrix inverse can not be performed using this method, as there is a residual phase ambiguity between the separate rows of the matrix due to the unknown phase distribution of the reference speckle pattern.

A map of the typical efficiencies achieved using this method is shown in figure 2d. These efficiencies are defined as the total intensity in the focal spot divided by the total intensity transmitted through the fibre. As can be seen in the figure, the typical efficiencies we achieve lie in the range of 20% to 25%, arranged in a roughly circular pattern. This circular pattern reflects the angular distribution of modes in the fibre, i.e. the density of modes as a function of polar angle k-vector component, as the spot efficiency is directly correlated with the number of fibre modes contributing to the local interference.

Using an internal reference that travels through the same fibre as the probes has the significant advantage of automatically matching the optical path lengths, thereby hugely simplifying the alignment of the characterisation setup. It does, however, lead to a speckle pattern as the actual reference signal, which in turn means that there are rows in the measured TM where the signal to noise of the measurement was not sufficient. In other words, there are a small number of unavoidable blank spots

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in the recovered images when using this method. These can also be seen quite clearly in the efficiency map of the reconstructed spots shown in figure 2d. On the whole though, this does not significantly appear to affect the quality of recovered images.

Imaging

Figure 4 - 3D imaging of a mannequin head, acquired by scanning a 59 by 59 pixel grid of illuminating spots and averaging over 500 laser pulses at each pixel, for a total acquisition time of approximately 400 seconds. a) Photograph of the scene being imaged, a mannequin head placed at approximately 50cm beyond the fibre distal ends; b) 3D reconstruction of the acquired image data in cartesian coordinates, with colour representing the reflectivity; c) measured reflectivities as a function of illumination angle; d) measured distances from the fibre as a function of illumination angle.

The most significant problem with extending MMF imaging of microscopic objects in the fibre near field to macroscopic objects in the far field is the restrictive etendue of the fibre aperture. This severely limits both the spatial resolution possible at larger distances, as well as the amount of backscattered light that can actually be collected without further collection optics. Even for imaging near the fibre facet the latter already complicates the ability to distinguish between actual backscattered light and light reflected by the fibre facets themselves. On the microscopic scale that problem can be mitigated by using, for example, fluorescence imaging and a wavelength filter, but that is clearly not feasible at macroscopic distances. While in principle the time of flight measurement should effectively time gate

the signal and alleviate the latter issue, the low reflected light levels captured by the fibre remains a challenge. We have therefore chosen to employ a second MMF with the same NA but a larger $500\mu\text{m}$ core diameter as the collection aperture for our current work, which is positioned parallel and in close proximity to the illuminating fibre.

The near end of the collecting MMF is placed in direct contact with the $500\mu\text{m}$ square sensor of a high speed APD to limit any further losses. The signal from this APD is then sampled using the high speed digitiser mentioned before. A reference photodiode in the opposite diffraction order of the DMD from the one used to control the illumination provides the trigger signal with respect to which the time of flight is measured. The actual distance beyond the MMFs is then calibrated using a white screen placed at several distances beyond the distal end of the fibres to take into account optical and electronic path length differences between the imaging arm and the reference arm.

Figure 5 - 3D imaging of a sparse scene, acquired by scanning a 59 by 59 pixel grid of illuminating spots and averaging over 500 laser pulses at each pixel, for a total acquisition time of approximately 400 seconds. a) Photograph of the scene being imaged, a snowman figurine placed at 30cm (right) and a dinosaur figurine at 40cm (left); b) 3D reconstruction of the acquired image data in cartesian coordinates, with colour representing the reflectivity; c) measured reflectivities as a function of illumination angle; d) measured distances from the fibre as a function of illumination angle.

The resulting signals are in the form of histograms of signal against time, with one histograms per pulse, as shown in figure 3. The intensities are corrected by multiplying by t^2 to take into account the quadratic signal decay with distance. Ideally each histogram would correspond to the illumination of a single angle in the far field. However, as can be seen in figure 2, in actuality the majority of the illuminating power is still concentrated in the background speckle patterns. As a result the measured histograms are a convolution of the reflectivities of the entire scene with the reflectivity of the target angle. To first approximation the background speckle patterns can be considered as a uniform illumination of the scene. A simple but effective approximation to deconvoluting the signal is therefore to subtract the average measured histogram (multiplied by an empirically from each individual histogram to leave only the contribution from the desired spot. While this introduces a slight error to the recovered reflectivities and associated distances, especially due to the variation in spot efficiency

Figure 6 – Time of flight measurements of a white screen placed at a shallow angle to the optical axis at 30cm beyond fibre for axial resolution measurement. a) Map of the acquired distances by illumination angle; b) graph of cartesian reconstructed coordinates within the region of interest indicated in (a), projected onto the xz-plane, with a linear fit as a means of determining the depth accuracy of the system. The RMSE of this fit is 1.5mm.

across the field of view, it is far more computationally practical than a full deconvolution approach and, especially for slowly varying scenes, the results are very close to the real scenes.

To reconstruct 3D images from these corrected datasets we take the location of the maximum value in the histograms as the distance and take the average signal in the total histograms as a measure of the reflectivity. Two examples of the results of this approach can be seen in figures 4 and 5.

Resolution, depth of field and acquisition time

There are two theoretical resolution limits in the system, axial and lateral. The former is determined by many factors, but in practice is limited by the sampling rate of the digitiser used to create the temporally resolved histograms from the analogue photodiode signals. For our current experiment this is 2.5GHz, or 0.4ns per bin, which corresponds to 60mm actual distance between bins of the histogram. As this still resolves the full pulse length of the laser, we can however improve upon this resolution by interpolating the histograms. The effectiveness of this is shown in figure 6, where a slanted white screen is used to measure the depth resolution of the system with an interpolation factor of 5. In theory this should give 2^5 times improved resolution, so ~ 1.9 mm, while as can be seen in the figure we reach ~ 1.5 mm here. Higher interpolation factors do not significantly improve the measured depth resolution.

The lateral angular resolution of the system expected by the Rayleigh criterion is

$$d\theta = 1.22 \frac{\lambda}{d} \approx 0.013 \text{ rad}, \quad (5)$$

for a d is $50\mu\text{m}$ the fibre core diameter, and λ is $0.532\mu\text{m}$ the laser wavelength. This lateral resolution was measured by imaging a flat slanted edge target and determining the modulation transfer function (MTF), as shown in figure 7. From the MTF we can extract a resolution of ~ 52 cycles per radian, or

Figure 7 - Analysis of the lateral resolution of our imaging system using a slanted edge target placed at 30cm beyond the fibres, perpendicular to the optical axis. a) Reflectivity map of the acquired image data as a function of illumination angle, with two regions of interest highlighted for which the MTF was calculated; b) the calculated MTF from the two regions indicated in (a). The dotted line was used as the noise level, and the intersection between the MTF curves and that line used to determine the lateral resolution.

$d\theta_{measured} = 1/\xi_{cutoff} \approx 0.019 \text{ rad}$, when measured at the radii corresponding to a high spot efficiency (compare with figure 3d.) In the centre the image quality is not sufficient to get a usable MTF curve or resolution, but the resolution is clearly worse. It therefore seems reasonable to ascribe the difference between the measured lateral resolution and the Rayleigh criterion to the relatively low spot efficiencies throughout the field of view, though this requires further study.

The depth of field of the system is limited by the quadratic drop off in intensity with distance, as well as the dynamic range and noise in the high speed APD. The interplay between these results in a minimum distance at which the detector nearly saturates, and a maximum distance at which the signal to noise ratio becomes too low. Furthermore, the measured signal also reduces proportionally to the reflectivity of the scene, which further limits the effective depth of field. While the noise level can be reduced and therefore the depth of field extended to a degree by averaging over multiple pulses per pixel, this clearly significantly increases the acquisition time. With our detector the effective depth of field is approximately five times the closest distance resolvable, which was set to be at ~20cm beyond the distal end of the fibres.

Finally the acquisition time of the system is fundamentally limited here by the repetition time of the laser, as at least one pulse per pixel is required to acquire an image. A second limit is set by the switching rate of the DMD, but in our case the latter is 22kHz while the laser repetition rate is ~7.5kHz, so the DMD in principle does not limit the acquisition time. Optimal use of the system would require approximately 2000 pixels in circular field of view, so would in principle make a >3Hz frame rate possible with this laser, or >10Hz with a faster repetition rate laser. In practice, however, our synchronisation between detector and DMD leads to about 40% of the pulses being lost. Therefore, we can acquire in the order of 4000 histograms per second. Furthermore we scan a square image for simplicity which means about twice as many pixels scanned, so this pixel rate leads to slightly less

than a single pass over a 59x59 pixel image. Finally, to get an acceptable image quality some averaging of multiple histograms per pixel is required, with 500 averages used for the figures shown here, making our actual acquisition time approximately 400 seconds per 3D image, though acceptable images can be found already at 50 averages per pixel, or about 1 minute per frame.

Conclusions

We have demonstrated a 3D imaging system based on scanning Lidar techniques operating through a set of two 20cm long multimode optical fibres. After an initial straightforward characterisation scheme 3D images with a lateral resolution of 19mrad and an axial resolution of 1.5mm were recovered from up to 60cm beyond the distal ends of the fibres, with no optics necessary at the imaging end of the fibres. These results are a first step towards endoscopes with diameter of only several hundred micrometres capable of imaging macroscopic scenes, which has clear applications in minimally invasive imaging modalities such as healthcare and security.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable concludes the parts of pure theory aimed to improve the protein analysis. The results are very encouraging and we also have a theory for further developments during and beyond the end of the project.

We selected the most promising approaches and the main directions for the development of protein sorter. One is based on extension of the OAM sorter and one on “single pixel detector” with sparse sampling.

Our development of protein recognition (Chapter 1) in the context of information theory, discrimination theory and with a tight analogy with the density matrix formalism in quantum mechanics.

The theory indicates how to write the maximum probability of differentiating between two model of proteins and confirms that the main problem is in the nature of proteins as weak phase object.

Chapter 2 we developed a different approach based on “single pixel detector” and we demonstrate that an iterative approach to image could be used to speed up the convergence.

It will be interesting in future to merget hese two ideas.

The single pixel detector approach is based on aberration but we believe we can use a series of electrodes to produce a different series of phase masks. This would be a separate approach to the projected structure retrieval and simulation shows that it can be pushed even to overcome the diffraction limits.

Chapter 3 is based on caustics and is not substantially different from the previous approach if not in the possibility of using more general phase elements.

Chapter 4 is more based on the use of time resolved and as anticipated in the previous version results quite speculative in this moment.

To conclude we have now enough material to project the next generation of device like programmable phase plates. Detailed simulations of the field in the device are still ongoing.

ANNEX 1:

REFEREE: Roberto Balboni (CNR-IMM Bologna, Italy)

I find this deliverable very fascinating and full of ideas that could keep researchers in electron microscopy busy for the next 5 years.

I find in particular very interesting the connection with different fields in both optics and quantum discrimination. I am sure these will become highly cited papers.

I have corrected a few typos. I am sorry of considering the large amount of work I may have missed some.

I have a particular comment on the analogy to the density matrix approach. I find the analogy very powerful and interesting to devise an optimal measurement basis even for considering the uncertainty on the 3D orientation.

Still I find an interesting pitfall of this formal analogy: in a mixed state or classic mix every electron is characterized by a different state $k=1$ or $K=2$, every electron is a different story and the actual state can be 1 or 2 each time. In the case of our system the protein is the same for every electrons with time we could improve our guess of the protein.

We thank the reviewer for the kind contribution and we understand the full deliverable is again very long to read. The question about the mixed state is indeed very interesting. As most of the paper is on single electron discrimination the formalism remains perfectly valid. However the generalization to many electron is more complicated. Notice in particular that our formula on many electron is calculated in a simplified case while in general a superposition of 2 binomial is to be used and the result needs to be calculated numerically. We are working on this more general scheme.

Notice also that the fact that the outcome of the n measurements is somehow correlated could allow for the iterative methods described for example in chapter 2 and in general also for a Bayesian inference approach.

We neglected this in this version.

REFEREE: AMIR TAVABI (FZJ , GER)

I am very excited by the results of these simulations: I really think we should try all these ideas in the microscope. I find the work well written whereas I would have enjoyed a more direct terminology match with the electron microscopy experiments. I am very interested in the actual implementation of the devices in the microscope.

I think you should give more details about how you are planning to implement this in the microscope.

Moreover I remember that the previous release of the deliverable featured a numerical implementation of a protein specific sorter. Why is this disappeared here?

We thank the reviewer. We are aware that we should do a further effort to unify the language between the two souls of the project. This has been done in particular for those ideas that we considered more promising.

I can give you some ideas on how we could plan experiment in chapter 1 . In facts the TITAN HOLO as you know features 3 different aperture planes so we can have space for a third phase element in the second SAD plane. The feasibility of this approach will depend on the new maintenance work of the microscope.

As for the other two ideas in chapter 2,3 I would say that the best implementation would be based on mounting an appropriate MEMS device in the objective aperture and using as many contacts as possible. The actual geometry needs to be decided trough Finite element simulatiосn as described in the upcoming deliverables.

As the protein specific sorter based on numerical optimization we decided to drop it for the moment. But we aim to conduct further studies.

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Multi Modal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL